

INVESTIGATIONS ON THE PROCESS STRATEGY OF LASER REMOTE CUTTING OF CARBON FIBER REINFORCED PLASTICS WITH A THICKNESS OF MORE THAN 5 MM

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ABSTRACT

Laser cutting of CFRP becomes an issue since production volumes of CFRP-parts in automotive and aerospace industry are increasing. This paper deals with the process strategy of the remote cutting approach and its adaptively to laminates with a thickness greater than 5 mm. The strategy is varied in 3 different approaches in order to maximize the cutting depth while keeping the heat affected zone at minimum. The experiments have shown that the cutting depth is a linear function to the number of passes up to a certain depth, dependent on process speed and laser power. When changing the strategy to parallel passes, to avoid shadowing the laser beam as well as retracing the focus, the cutting depth can be increased up to 13 mm while the HAZ stays around 200 μm .

1 INTRODUCTION

Electrical driven cars are one of the main approaches to archive the governmental objective to reduce carbon dioxide emissions. However the necessary batteries for electrifying the engine-systems lead to a noticeable increase in the weight of the vehicle. Therefore, in automotive industry, carbon fiber reinforced structures become an important part of the material mix, used to design lightweight cars such as the BMW i3-model. The high potential of CFRP-parts for lightweight construction, however, comes with high manufacturing costs [1]. Large shares of those costs are due to cutting, trimming and drilling operations. The extremely high tool-wear leads to unsteady cutting qualities and high tool costs while using conventional machining processes. Cutting CFRP with laser leads to a wear-free, nearly force-free and fast process [2]. Yet, classical laser-cutting systems with a fixed optic, which is following the cutting-path, are limited in speed and thus resulting in high temperature damage of the cutting edge. First research results already show the potential of remote cutting by using a scanning system [3]. Past experiments are mostly carried out, cutting material with thicknesses up to 6 mm. Referring to automotive structural part, thicknesses can locally be greater than 6 mm. This paper deals with the process strategy of cutting such material with the remote scanning head. The focus lays on the development of a 2D cutting process for thick laminate with the state of the art multi pass strategy while maximizing quality and effective process speed.

2 STATE OF THE ART

Laser cutting of CFRP is being investigated by several groups, following different approaches while focusing on a high process speed and reducing the damage of the cutting kerf, mostly characterized by the heat affected zone (HAZ). The physically possible minimum damage is investigated by Weber et al. [4] by using a perpendicular heat flow model. The result is that the minimal achievable HAZ is a function of the laser intensity. Considering the state of the art of laser systems, only pulsed laser sources are capable of generating the necessary intensities. However the average output power of pulsed systems is considerably lower than of continuous wave (cw) systems thus resulting in a low effective process speed.

An approach to reach the high desired intensities and short interaction times with a cw system is presented by Bluemel et al. [5] by increasing laser power as well as increasing process speed. It is suggested, that the low resulting interaction time yields in less time for heat conduction. Following this approach, Klotzbach et al. [3] is increasing the process speed further by using a scanning system while maintaining the level of laser power which is resulting in a multi pass strategy in order to cut the whole laminate. This introduces the new parameter of the time delay between the passes. This “remote” approach uses a scanning system to achieve the high process speeds of >1 m/s. Minimizing the delay between the passes yields into a higher HAZ as it can be shown by Stock et al. [6]. It is assumed that low delays yield in a heat accumulation at the kerf thus increasing the HAZ.

Laminate thicknesses of past experiments vary between 1-6 mm. Emmelmann et al. where cutting laminates successfully up to a thickness of 4 mm [7]. Remote processes using cw laser sources where carried out by Fuchs et al. and Jung et al. reaching material thicknesses of 3 mm [8, 9]. The thickest laminate at 6 mm is ablated by Denkena et al. using a pulsed laser system and focussing on ablation processes rather than cutting processes [10]. The usage of a laser source with an average output power of 5 W however does not make this process suitable for automotive cutting applications.

3 APPROACH

Since the aim is to investigate the feasible maximum material thickness, the experiment is focusing on measuring the depth of a cutting kerf of a thick laminate of approximately 15 mm. Aiming at maximum cutting depth, in a first step the concept of a multi pass strategy is being extended by increasing the numbers of passes up to the point, where the cutting depth reaches a level of no progress. The process speed is fixed at 2 m/s. Since heat accumulation is likely to occur with a high number of passes, a high delay of 2 s is set in order to avoid this effect for the experiments. In the second step, for further increasing the cutting depth, the focus is being retraced when the depth progress comes to a hold. In a third and last step, the effect of a curved kerf-geometry which occurs in step 1 is being avoided by adjusting parallel passes and focus diameter.

4 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

For the experiments a 2D scanning system (figure 1) was used in combination with a high-power Yb:YAG disk laser with a process fiber of 100 μm . In order to achieve the high intensities necessary to sublimate the material at high speed, the focal length of the scanning system was changed to 255 mm. This system configuration leads to an image scale of $S = 1:0.54$, thus to a focal diameter of 185 μm . Assuming a top hat beam profile, the maximum intensity is at $2.23 \times 10^7 \text{ W/cm}^2$. According to [4] this intensity should lead to a theoretical minimum damage of approximately 100 μm .

Figure 1: Experimental Setup

Laser System			
Manufacturer	TRUMPF GmbH + Co. KG, Ditzingen, Germany		
Type	TruDisk 6001		
Wavelength	λ	nm	1030
Maximum power output	P_{\max}	kW	6
Beam parameter product	BPP	mm·mrad	4
Process fiber diameter	d_{fib}	μm	100
Scanning System			
Manufacturer	TRUMPF GmbH + Co. KG, Ditzingen, Germany		
Type	PFO 33		
Focal length	f	mm	255
Image scale	S	mm	1:0.54
Elliptical scanning field size	-	mm*mm	104*180
Maximum feeding rate	v_{Max}	m/s	10
Maximum Laser Power	P_{Max}	kW	10
Beam characteristics (measured)			
			1 kW
			6 kW
Focal diameter	d_f	μm	172
Rayleigh length	z_R	mm	1,9

Table 1: Laser system characteristics

The material used for the experiments is based on a typical automotive fiber fabric. The CFRP-laminate is manufactured using unidirectional layers of non-crimp fabric in 0° orientation. The material thickness of approximately 15 mm is achieved by adding 60 layers of fabric.

Material characteristics	
Fiber system	HS carbon – T700

Fabric type	Unidirectional non-crimp fabric
Areal weight	200 g/m ²
Epoxy resin	CHS-EPOXY 474
Epoxy hardener	TELALIT 0420
Weight parts hardener : resin	22:100
Cured Material characteristics	
Material thickness	14-16 mm
Number of UD layers	60
Nominal resin content	approx. 50 vol.%
Specimen measurements (length * width)	100 mm * 20 mm

Table 2: Material characteristics

The cutting process was carried out with the focus on material surface of the specimen and with a cutting length of 40 mm. Since the specimen is only 20 mm in length, the cutting depth can be estimated at the side of the specimen.

After the cutting process the specimen are embedded in an epoxy dipping and polished with a 9 μm diamond polish. The resulting cross sections are being measured focusing on the heat affected zone and the geometry of the kerf (figure 2). The average lateral extension of the HAZ is calculated by dividing the area of the HAZ A_{HAZ} by the kerf depth t_K .

Figure 2: Cross section measurement of kerf geometry

Cross section measurement		
Kerf depth	t_K	μm
Kerf width	b_K	μm
Heat affected zone	A_{HAZ}	μm ²
Average lateral extension of the heat affected zone	b_{HAZ}	μm

Table 3: Nomenclature

5 RESULTS

Step 1: Increasing passes

The number of passes was increased starting from 1 until no more progress in depth is noticeable at the side of the specimen.

Step 1: Parameters		
Laser power	kW	6
Focus position	mm	0
Process speed	m/s	2
Delay	s	2
Total number of passes	-	1-85

Table 4: Parameters for step 1

The results are shown at figure 3. It can be noted, that the cutting depth is increasing linear with the number of passes until a kerf depth of approximately 5 mm is reached. Adding more passes has significantly less effect on the kerf depth. By using a linear regression the turning point can be determined at 17 passes. At a depth of 5 mm the laser beam reaches the bottom of the kerf is out of the Rayleigh length. This effect suggests a high reflection of the laser beam at the kerf edge. The effect of the increasing passes and depth on the heat affected zone is minimal since it levels between 130 and 220 μm .

Figure 3: Results of step 1 at 6 kW laser power and cross section of kerf at 5.8 mm depth

At high cutting depths the figures show a significantly higher spreading. Examining the cross sections of those specimens, it can be observed that some of the kerfs are curving (figure 3). Those curved kerfs can only occur if a high percentage of the laser power is being reflected at the kerf side as already suggested before. The inhomogeneity of the material might influence the degree of reflection leading to an uneven sublimation on either side of the kerf. This effect hinders further increase in depth.

Step 2: Retracing focus

The cutting depth shows a linear progress with increasing passes up to a certain depth. After this linear section, the depth is making less progress with each pass. The linear progress is steeper for low process speeds. It is assumed that the reflected laser beam at the kerf side is becoming the larger compared with the un-reflected, direct beam with increasing depth. Since with every reflection, a part of the energy remains as absorbed energy in the kerf side, the reflected beam power is decreasing with increasing depth. In step 2 the focus position is retraced after the turning point is reached at 5 mm depth. The experiment is carried out with 6 kW laser power while repositioning the focus after 17 passes to 5 mm beneath the specimen surface in order increase the intensity of the laser power at the bottom of the kerf.

Step 2: Parameters		
Laserpower	kW	6
Focusposition	mm	0-5
Process speed	m/s	2
Delay	s	2
Number of passes	-	1-85

Table 5: Parameters for step 2

The results show no improvements in kerf depth (figure 4). However after repositioning the focus the kerf width is more than doubling in size. It seems self-evident that the wider beam spot at the top surface that results of the repositioning is the reason for the increased kerf width. It is assumed that the material at the top surface is also shadowing off the beam so the intensity at the bottom of the kerf is not increasing after repositioning the focus. As it can be seen in the cross section in figure 5, the curved kerf geometry is still visible, leading to an uneven cutting kerf when repositioning the focus.

Figure 4: Kerf depth and cross section and width before and after repositioning of focus

Step 3: Parallel passes

Two effects became evident in the first two experiments that hinder further increase in kerf depth. First, the reflecting beam can lead to an uneven kerf sublimation which causes curved kerf geometry. Second, retracing the focus position causes shadowing of the beam and thus a loss of intensity at the bottom of the kerf. It is assumed that the curved geometry is appearing at a depth, where the ablation by the reflected beam becomes greater than the ablation by direct beam interaction. Reflected beam ablation however increases with increasing depth, since double and triple reflections occur and overlapping each other. At small kerf depths the direct beam interaction with the material is assumed to be the major ablation energy input.

In Step 3 the solution is provided by repositioning the focus in smaller steps to avoid ablation by a reflected beam as well as increasing the kerf width by parallel passes in order to avoid shadowing of the beam.

To define the length of the focus repositioning step, the depth is determined at which the curved kerf geometry appears. The previous cut geometries are measured by defining a symmetry line normal to the specimen surface and through the midpoint of the kerf entry. The symmetry line is intersecting with the kerf sides indicating the beginning of the curved geometry. The depth of the intersection is being measured for several specimen, leading to a mean value of 3.9 mm (figure 5 A) The focus should be repositioned before this value so the curved geometry is avoided. For the experiments, a repositioning step of 2.5 mm was chosen (B).

Figure 5: Process Strategy of parallel passes and focus position

The distance between the parallel passes is chosen by the kerf width at the entry. It is typically around 0.2 mm (see figure 4) which correlates with the focus diameter. The number of parallel passes is

chosen by referring to the beam caustic. First, the target depth is set to 15 mm. At a focus repositioning step of 2.5 mm the last focus position is at 12.5 mm (figure 5 D). The beam diameter at the kerf entrance at this focus position can be calculated at 1.13 mm. Divided by the kerf width of 0.2 mm for each pass results in 6 parallel passes, necessary to avoid shadowing of the beam at the kerf entrance.

Step 3: Parameters		
Laser power	W	6000
Focus position	mm	0-12.5
Focus shift depth	mm	2,5
Process speed	m/s	2
Delay	s	2
Number of total passes	-	1-168
Number of parallel passes	-	6-1
Number of passes for each parallel pass	-	8

Table 6: Parameters for step 3

Referring to the results of Step 1 (figure 3), the depth for each pass is determined at 0.31 mm. At each focus position, each parallel pass is repeated 8 times in order to reach a depth of 2.5 mm. That is followed by a repositioning of the focus to 2.5 mm beneath the previous position. In order to reduce heat accumulation, the sequence of the passes is altered.

Figure 6: Cross sections of parallel passes result

Figure 7: Result of step 3 – parallel passes with focus repositioning

The Result shows a continuing depth progress with increasing passes (Figure 7). However, the increase in depth is behaving different than expected. At the first layer, the depth is at 4.3 mm significantly deeper than planned while at the last layer, the final depth is at 12.7 mm while 15 mm where expected. The kerf geometry still shows signs of a curved symmetry line.

6 DISCUSSION AND OUTLOOK

The experiments of step 1 show a linear correlation of the number of passes and the kerf depth. This confirms the results of previous experiments [8]. However the depth progress is slowing down significantly at a depth of approximately 6 mm while the spreading increases at the same time. It is assumed that the reflection at the cutting kerf is the main factor for this effect (figure 8). A part of the laser beam is being reflected at the cutting kerf direct as well as scattered while the other part is being absorbed. If the absorbed energy input is high enough to sublimate the material, the kerf is widening and increasing in depth. The direct reflected beam is interacting with the opposite kerf wall, leading to a repetition of the effects. Since the laser beam is losing intensity with each reflection, caused by the absorption at the wall, the effect decreases with increasing depth. It is assumed that the absorbed energy input is reaching a critical level at a kerf depth of 6 mm for the given parameters which leads to less ablation of material.

The curved kerf geometry can explain the spreading. The latter is a result of the inhomogeneity of the material. The reflection on each side of the kerf wall depends on the local nominal resin content. The resulting inconsistency of the proportion between absorption and reflection leads to an asymmetry of sublimation.

Figure 8: Beam reflection and absorption at the kerf walls

The experiments prove that the curved geometry can be reduced by repositioning the focus position. The results of step 3 show significant improvement in kerf depth. The calculated depth however does not correlate with the resulting depth. Operating with parallel passes changes the kerf geometry significantly as well as the reflection effects. A main influence is assumed to be the process strategy. Each parallel pass consists of 8 passes. The sequence in which those passes are carried out leads to different kerf geometries and thus to different reflection effects during the process. Another effect influenced by the strategy is the heat accumulation. Parallel kerfs which are sublimated sequentially, lead to high heat accumulation in the material between.

The results of the cutting process stand in competition to conventional processes such as milling and water jet cutting. The main advantages of the laser are the lack of wear as well as the high feed rate. The last advantage however, is being reduced since the cutting process is operating in several layers. Figure 9 shows the resulting process speed over the achieved cutting depth for the laser process as well as conventional technologies. It can be seen that the laser process is faster up to a thickness of about 5-6 mm. Further experiments are needed to increase process speed for laminates thicker than 5 mm. This can be achieved by optimizing the process strategy of parallel passes. The use of a single mode laser source should also have large effects on the achievable depth and feed rate since the beam is less likely to be shadowed at the kerf entry and the intensities can be chosen significantly higher. Last but not least the process delay needs further investigations in order to reduce the overall process time.

Figure 9: Comparison of process speed of laser cutting versus conventional processes

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